

Current issues of teaching English

Minnibaeva Galina Igorevna

Tashkent region, Kibrary district, school 24.

Abstract: Current issues of teaching English are focused on effective, modern and innovative methods of teaching English to increase interest in learning the language.

Key words: mixed techniques, fun games, modern innovative techniques, pantomime, tasks.

“Today’s decisions in the field of educational policy have a wide impact on the scientific, economic, political and cultural needs of the country,” says Daria observer, expert of the Great Future group of the South Korean district of Busan, professor at the University of Languages Azamat Akbarov. The system of teaching foreign languages to children at an early age, which has been introduced in some countries since the 1990s, also corresponds to our country, and in 2017-2018 it was proposed to adopt some legislative acts in this area.

Language learning as a child

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Any child showing a normal level of development is able to learn any language that he encounters in the environment in which he lives and has the potential to communicate with other people. Reducing the number of languages that a child can learn from a neurological point of view is not the topic of our conversation. On the contrary, every child without a pathological defect can learn two, three or more languages. However, a child's level of proficiency in each language varies from one language to another, depending on the need to use that language and the environment. Many studies today show that learning a foreign language in childhood can be successful if it is carried out using appropriate methods and approaches. However, this can only be achieved if language teaching methods and learning materials are appropriate for the learning level of students. There are two main conditions for this: the student's ability to communicate in a foreign language environment and the use of the foreign language being studied, as well as the use of the language being studied in meaningful contexts.

Not enough classes per week

As in our country, in systems where a foreign language is limited to the course, time and speed of language learning are important. 5-7 years to acquire knowledge of listening, speaking, reading, writing and vocabulary and to apply all these skills in a foreign language from an academic point of view correctly and flawlessly. There should be a curriculum that provides for regular and effective sessions. From this point of view, a week of foreign language classes in grades 2, 3 and 4 is not enough. Language teaching, which is naturally a means of both written and oral communication, requires continuity. A 7-8 year old primary school student

may not be able to master a foreign language system that only allows him to communicate 4-5 hours a week and cannot be used in his own environment.

Textbooks should not be the only source of knowledge

Another major problem in language teaching is the methods and equipment used for language teaching. When studying textbooks used at the primary level in general education schools, it became clear that there is no connection between components between topics and no connection between units of vocabulary, despite the myriad of Ladi dictionaries. When we use language in every situation in life, every word that comes out of our mouths is semantically related to what was said before or after. At a time when technology is advancing rapidly, there is no doubt that textbooks should not be the only source of language learning. Considering that in 80% of cases our teachers use textbooks when teaching foreign languages throughout the country, it is necessary to pay special attention to the preparation of other textbooks and additional teaching materials. Today we are in a situation where a child of 7-8 years old, who started learning a foreign language in the 2nd grade of elementary school, finished the 4th grade last week or last night in the language he learned. I have been studying for 3 years. I cannot tell the action that took place.

Because the content of textbooks used in elementary school does not allow this.

Some languages are learned at an early age

In the early stages of learning a foreign language, one can observe the influence of the characteristics of the native language of students. This situation, called

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"interlingual interaction", indicates that there is always a connection between the native language in the memory of the student and the other language that he began to learn. In addition, many aspects of language development slow down in language learning. Some features and aspects of the language are acquired earlier, and some later. Sometimes it takes a long time to master many seemingly simple aspects due to differences in languages. If the learner is unable to hear and use the language, he or she will not be able to make positive progress in language learning and will soon forget what he or she has already learned.

Learning a foreign language is not a miracle

Each material presented in a language study should be meaningful, and the topics should be related to each other and, if necessary, to other things that the child has learned in other lessons. In this case, foreign language teachers are obliged to work together and make plans together with other teachers leading this class. It also requires that the experience and life of each student be considered and linked in the learning process. In this context, content models, fairy tales and songs can be used in the educational process, corresponding to the levels of cognitive, linguistic and social development and activities in which students are directly involved. In short, given that more than half of the world's population speaks two or more languages in everyday life, we are convinced that learning a foreign language is not a miracle. In addition, we can teach a foreign language to a student, not only as an opportunity for a few people to succeed, but also so that they can keep up with the times.

CONCLUSION

In short, they can learn a language not as a duty, but through fun games and innovative methods that can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, although the education system is also faced with the task of educating a free-thinking, comprehensively developed, mature person, in the future we, future teachers, will be able to develop our own ways of effectively using innovative technologies. contribute.

RECOMMENDATIONS

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